

How to use and contribute to a software sustainability dashboard

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Engineering and
Physical Sciences
Research Council

Get your phones/laptops
ready:

We will use [menti.com](https://www.menti.com) &
QR codes for Interactive
surveying

“meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.”

Sustainability: UN 1987

An RSE collaboration between **Scikit-Surgery**

Library of tools for surgical navigation,
actively developed by researchers in
**Wellcome / EPSRC Centre for
Interventional and Surgical Sciences
(WEISS)**

Scikit-Surgery libraries implements a family of compact, orthogonal, libraries accompanied by robust testing, documentation, and quality control. Scikit-Surgery libraries can be rapidly assembled into testable clinical applications and subsequently translated to production software without the need for software reimplementations.

Getting started:

Wondering which library is suitable for your job and how to use it? Check out the list of included libraries, relevant documentation and [demo tutorials](#).

Packages:

Library	Purpose
scikit-surgerycore	Algorithms/tools common to all scikit-surgery packages. Read more...
scikit-surgeryimage	Image processing algorithms using OpenCV. Read more...
scikit-surgeryvtk	Implements VTK functionality for IGS applications. Read more...
scikit-surgeryutils	Example applications/utilities. Read more...

and UCL's Advanced Center for Research Computing

Guided by fundamental principles of Open Source Software and Collaboration

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Open Source Software Sustainability Funding Call

Project: Open-source tools for Encouraging Sustainability in Diverse Multi-Library Projects

As Scikit-Surgery,

“we have developed a single sustainability dashboard ... that pulls together some of the publicly available measures of software sustainability onto a single dynamic webpage”

- keeping track of their (evolving) research community
- fundraising

The existing sustainability dashboard

deployed in <https://scikit-surgery.github.io/scikit-surgery-stats/>

scikitsurgery library status

Library	Total Weeks Up	Latest Release Date	CI Status	Docs	Coverage	Lines of Code	Downloads with Mirror	Stars	Forks	Watchers	Contributors	Package Health	V
scikit-surgeryimage	Weeks Up 242	Last Release 2022-03-22	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 93%	LOC 5372	downloads 988	Stars 0	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 4	package health 44/100	
scikit-surgerycore	Weeks Up 241	Last Release 2022-02-08	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 98%	LOC 3382	downloads 75k	Stars 4	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 6	package health 44/100	
scikit-surgeryoverlay	Weeks Up 238	Last Release 2019-01-02	CI Status coverage unknown	docs unknown	coverage unknown		downloads 9k					package health 36/100	
scikit-surgeryvideotools	Weeks Up 238	Last Release 2018-12-23	CI Status coverage unknown	docs unknown	coverage unknown		downloads 5k					package health 36/100	
scikit-surgeryvtk	Weeks Up 235	Last Release 2023-06-20	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 91%	LOC 6269	downloads 103k	Stars 16	Forks 4	Watchers 4	Contrib 7	package health 66/100	
ndcube	Weeks Up 234	Last Release 2023-01-11	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs unknown	coverage unknown	LOC 7268	downloads 159k	Stars 2	Forks 2	Watchers 2	Contrib 12	package health 56/100	
scikit-surgeryndtracker	Weeks Up 234	Last Release 2023-04-19	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 61%	LOC 2026	downloads 35k	Stars 29	Forks 10	Watchers 4	Contrib 7	package health 61/100	
scikit-surgeryutils	Weeks Up 232	Last Release 2023-06-22	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 40%	LOC 2372	downloads 42k	Stars 3	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 5	package health 69/100	
scikit-surgerypdcpp	Weeks Up 222	Last Release 2020-06-13	CI Status build passing	docs missing	coverage unknown	LOC 14407	downloads 118k	Stars 2	Forks 0	Watchers 6	Contrib 2	package health 39/100	
OMakeCatchTemplate	Weeks Up 222	Last Release 2019-03-05	CI Status build passing	docs unknown	coverage unknown	LOC 13669	downloads 175k	Stars 25	Forks 12	Watchers 4	Contrib 4	package health 39/100	
scikit-surgeryopencvcpp	Weeks Up 222	Last Release 2020-06-09	CI Status coverage unknown	docs unknown	coverage unknown	LOC 13274	downloads 185k	Stars 0	Forks 3	Watchers 6	Contrib 2	package health 39/100	
scikit-surgeryk	Weeks Up 225	Last Release 2022-03-01	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 42%	LOC 2298	downloads 13k	Stars 0	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 2	package health 52/100	
scikit-surgeryyasttracker	Weeks Up 223	Last Release 2023-04-27	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 100%	LOC 2673	downloads 29k	Stars 2	Forks 0	Watchers 4	Contrib 3	package health 64/100	
scikit-surgerydialmc	Weeks Up 218	Last Release 2020-10-06	CI Status coverage unknown	docs passing	coverage unknown	LOC 2618	downloads 5k					package health 38/100	
scikit-surgery-sphere-fitting	Weeks Up 216	Last Release 2021-07-27	CI Status ci.yml no status	docs passing	coverage 100%	LOC 1593	downloads 7k	Stars 1	Forks 0	Watchers 1	Contrib 1	package health 42/100	
scikit-surgerytostimulator	Weeks Up 215	Last Release 2021-07-21	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs unknown	coverage 100%		downloads 4k	Stars 0	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 3	package health 43/100	
scikit-surgeryspeck	Weeks Up 207	Last Release 2022-03-01	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 41%	LOC 1706	downloads 17k	Stars 0	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 5	package health 46/100	
mappyonic	Weeks Up 208	Last Release 2023-03-28	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 100%	LOC 2121	downloads 15k	Stars 10	Forks 2	Watchers 4	Contrib 3	package health 58/100	
scikit-surgery-evaluation	Weeks Up 188	Last Release 2022-03-02	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 81%	LOC 1928	downloads 8k	Stars 0	Forks 1	Watchers 2	Contrib 2	package health 48/100	
scikit-surgerytrackresidualization	Weeks Up 186	Last Release 2022-02-24	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 100%	LOC 2418	downloads 9k	Stars 1	Forks 0	Watchers 2	Contrib 1	package health 46/100	
scikit-surgeryif	Weeks Up 175	Last Release 2022-03-22	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 17%	LOC 2384	downloads 5k	Stars 1	Forks 0	Watchers 4	Contrib 5	package health 46/100	
scikit-surgerycalibration	Weeks Up 167	Last Release 2023-02-25	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 84%	LOC 5658	downloads 32k	Stars 5	Forks 1	Watchers 3	Contrib 4	package health 60/100	
scikit-surgeryboard	Weeks Up 167	Last Release 2023-06-28	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 89%	LOC 2924	downloads 9k	Stars 5	Forks 1	Watchers 4	Contrib 6	package health 66/100	
scikit-surgerygata	Weeks Up 161	Last Release 2022-03-24											
scikit-surgeryfret	Weeks Up 160	Last Release 2022-01-26	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 93%	LOC 3928	downloads 16k	Stars 2	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 1	package health 44/100	
scikit-surgerysysfacematch	Weeks Up 160	Last Release 2020-10-22	CI Status coverage unknown	docs passing	coverage 91%	LOC 2710	downloads 16k	Stars 1	Forks 0	Watchers 2	Contrib 2	package health 42/100	

Metrics displayed in our dashboard

Metrics (default)	Source	Definition
Total weeks up	Github Repo	Created date
Last Update Date	Github Repo	Last activity in default branch
Lines of Code	Github Repo + cloc tool	Total lines of code in latest version of default branch
Stars	Github Repo	
Forks	Github Repo	
Watchers	Github Repo	
Contributors	Github Repo	

Metrics displayed in our dashboard

Metrics (optional: based on availability)	Source	Definition
CI Status	PyPI.org ->	Latest GHA status from <code>.github/workflows</code>
Docs	PyPI.org ->	Docs coverage badge from <code>readthedocs.org</code>
Coverage	PyPI.org ->	Coverage stats from <code>coveralls.io</code>
Downloads with Mirror	PyPI.org ->	stats from <code>pepy.tech</code>
Package Health	PyPI.org ->	definition from <code>snky.io/advisor</code> : Not described but there a table that suggests it is a combined score of “security” + “popularity” + “maintenance” + “community”
Maintainability	PyPI.org ->	Definition from <code>codeclimate.org</code> : Maintainability is an estimate of technical debt in the repo based on a standardized 10-point assessment of Duplication, Cyclomatic Complexity, Cognitive Complexity, and structural issues.”

Our simple deployment strategy


```
schedule:  
- cron: '0 */12 * * *' # Redeploy the dashboard every 12 hours
```

To : Github-pages of the organisation,

CI : embedded within a Github-Action, cron scheduled

Triggers a set of python scripts that pull & format data and generate the html's of dashboard

GitHub Pages

Dashboard Template

(Create your own dashboards using our template and github actions)

<https://github.com/SciKit-Surgery/sustainable-pkg-stats>

Cookieninja - A Cookiecutter Fork

PyPI v1.0.0 Python 3.7 | 3.8 | 3.9 | 3.10 CI/CD Tests passing codecov 100% docs passing Scrutinizer 9.14

A command-line utility that creates projects from `cookiecutters` (project templates), e.g. creating a Python package project from a Python package project template.

Includes

- Analysis pipeline
- Dashboard html files
- Github Action to deploy to Pages

Needed

- Github Permissions
- target base Python library ex. `astropy` , `nif`

Some Example Dashboards

'scikit-surgery' https://thompson318.github.io/dashboard_for_scikit-surgery/

'Scikit' https://thompson318.github.io/dashboard_for_scikits/

'magpi' https://thompson318.github.io/dashboard_for_magpi/

'microbit' https://thompson318.github.io/dashboard_for_microbit/

'thompson318' https://thompson318.github.io/dashboard_for_thompson318/

Next: Make your own dashboard(s)

Instructions: <https://github.com/SciKit-Surgery/sustainable-pkg-stats>

Warning on runtimes:

'scikit-surgery' 56 libraries: ~ 15 minutes

'thompson318' : 24 libraries ~ 9 minutes

'microbit' : 185 libraries ~ 30 minutes

'magpi' : 382 libraries ~ 60 minutes

Workshop agenda

- Use our template to create your own dashboards (in teams or on your own):
<https://github.com/SciKit-Surgery/sustainable-pkg-stats>
- Get your dashboards running on GitHub actions
- Modify the scripts to suit your application.
- Share your Dashboards with us:
<https://github.com/SciKit-Surgery/sustainable-pkg-stats/discussions/22>
- [12:00] Discussions: what works / doesn't work.
- [12:15] We'll have a wrap up at the end using mentimeter.

Some ideas for customising your template

(time-permitting during this workshop)

- Github Action:
 - currently on [push, PR, cron] for workshop purposes: you can change the deployment style
 - remove/add analysis steps
- Specify the libraries to search for:
 - Searching for library names in pypi and github: `get_github_repos.py`, `get_pypi_repos.py`
 - Exclusions
 - Might be necessary for keeping the runtime: refer to `scikit` implementation
- Add library logo
- Adjust default text descriptions/styling in html files

Open-source tools for Encouraging Sustainability in Diverse Multi-Library Projects

As ARC + Scikit-Surgery,

our goals were to make this dashboard more **active**, **useful** and **versatile**

Our definitions rely on us understanding:

- What is “sustainability” and which metrics best capture this?
- How can researchers/RSEs outside of this domain use this dashboard as an example?
- ...

This is why...

we need insights from the research software community

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1bZUevP--HYrpCS_hbaWBhTSJ-h5sUDtn8/edit#slide=id.p5

Survey time!

Join us at [menti.com](https://www.menti.com)

Code: 8159 1768

Survey time!

<https://www.menti.com/alou9vy715g1>

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Take-away and thank you

- Sustainability dashboards can add value to open source research
- Metrics to benchmark sustainability are varied and can be hard to define
- We proposed a template for users to create their dashboards, and we want to hear from our community on what works/doesn't work, for our future work

Find me in RSE slack/
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for questions

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